

Joint Involvement in Dengue

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INTRODUCTION

Dengue fever (DF) and dengue haemorrhagic fever/dengue shock syndrome (DHF/DSS) are important mosquito-borne viral diseases affecting humans worldwide and constitute a major public health problem in tropical and subtropical regions. The four serotypes of dengue virus (DEN), a member of the *Flaviviridae* family of positive-sense single-stranded RNA viruses, cause a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations in humans ranging from the acute febrile illness DF to the life-threatening DHF/DSS. Dengue fever is a self-limited though debilitating disease characterized by headache, retro-orbital pain, myalgia, arthralgia, rash, and in some cases haemorrhagic manifestations; DHF is defined by haemorrhagic signs, thrombocytopenia, and haemoconcentration or other evidence of vascular leakage, and can progress to shock (DSS) and death.¹

ARTHRITIS

Rheumatic manifestations like joint pains are a major feature of dengue, although often overshadowed by other clinical features such as biphasic fever, skin rash, conjunctival suffusion, pharyngitis, headache, abdominal pain, vomiting, photophobia, orbital pain and haemorrhagic manifestations.^{1,2} The incidence of arthralgia varies from 3 to 82%.²⁻⁸ However, most of the series suggest that about 2/3rd individuals with dengue suffer from joint pains. Peripheral joints are predominantly involved.² Although about 2/3rd of patients with dengue have joint pains the distribution of the involved joints is not well described. During 1996 epidemic in Lucknow predominantly large joints were affected.³ Features of active synovitis like effusion and morning stiffness have not been described.²

As compared to adults, in paediatric population the incidence of joint pains is much lower.^{1,8} Phuong and colleagues have described joint pain only in 3% of their study population of 712 dengue affected children.⁸ Joint manifestations are not related to disease severity.¹⁻¹⁰ Persistent arthralgia or recurrence have not been described in dengue.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Many viral diseases can present with fever and arthralgia. If symptoms start more than two weeks after the patient has left a dengue-endemic area, or if the fever lasts more than two weeks, dengue can be effectively ruled out.^{9,10} Joint pains associated with joint effusions are seen in patients affected with Chikungunya virus. In this infection, arthritis and myalgias are the major manifestations. Alphavirus infections like sindbis virus infection, pogo fever, mayaro fever, ross river valley fever are associated with persistent arthralgia, recurrence of arthralgia or even presence of joint effusions.^{11,12,13} During the 2002 outbreak of dengue and leptospirosis in Mumbai, thrombocytopenia and arthralgia were significantly associated with dengue¹⁴. During concurrent epidemic of leptospirosis presence of arthralgia may serve as a pointer to differentiate the diseases clinically from Dengue. Five clinical features were significantly associated with leptospirosis, namely conjunctival suffusion, haemorrhage, abdominal pain, hepatosplenomegaly, and oedema.¹⁴

Treatment of joint pains is purely symptomatic. Because of associated thrombocytopenia NSAIDs should be avoided. However paracetamol can be given safely. In almost all patients joint pains disappear completely.

To summarize, joint pains are seen in about 2/3rd of patients with dengue predominantly affecting the peripheral joints without associated joint effusion. Persistence or recurrence of joint pains is not a feature of dengue and if present then alternative aetiology like alphavirus infections should be considered. During concurrent epidemic of similar illnesses like leptospirosis presence of arthralgia may be more suggestive of dengue. Only symptomatic treatment is needed and due to presence of thrombocytopenia NSAIDs's should be avoided.

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